

Half-cycle-by-half-cycle compensation driven by the RX residual and applied through a TX injection pulse for square-wave pulse induction detectors

Tony Kopp

Independent Researcher
ENIGMA/PI⁴ Project
Switzerland R&D Office
Zelgli 44
1716 Oberschrot, SWITZERLAND
Email: electronimagination@gmail.com

Willy Bayot

Independent Researcher
ENIGMA/PI⁴ Project
Belgium R&D Office
75 rue de la buscaille
6230 Obaix, BELGIUM
Email: WillyBayot@hotmail.com

Alexandre Tartar

Physicist Engineer
ENIGMA/PI⁴ Project
First Texas Products
France R&D Office
41 rue du Marais
62310 Fruges, FRANCE
Email: alexandre@frsttx.com

April 30, 2026

This work constitutes a public prior-art disclosure written in France, Belgium, Switzerland, and the United States. All technical elements are intentionally published in order to prevent their appropriation by third-party patent filings.

Abstract

This publication describes a compensation method for a square-wave pulse induction detector, in particular a bipolar square-wave PI detector in which the TX coil current switches between defined current states. The method is not directed to conventional sawtooth-current PI detectors, in which the energy of the TX coil is intentionally dissipated after each pulse and the coil is recharged by the following pulse.

The compensation error is observed on the receive side by direct ADC sampling of the RX signal, or by an equivalent low-latency sampled representation obtained after a short analog capture stage or a short analog integration stage, preferably after the RX preamplifier. In one implementation, a short group of capture windows is summed or averaged in order to estimate the residual RX error. This fast correction path deliberately avoids long digital filtering, long-term averaging, and high-latency processing, because such processing would be incompatible with half-cycle-by-half-cycle correction.

The corrective action is applied on the transmit side by an injection MOSFET. The compensation voltage V_{comp} is fixed and is not amplitude-modulated by the compensation loop. Adaptive correction is achieved exclusively by modifying the conduction duration T_{comp} of the TX injection MOSFET. The correction is updated and applied at each half-cycle, allowing rapid compensation of the imbalance visible at the receiver without directly measuring the slope of the TX current.

The central distinction from prior art based on TX-current feedback is that the correction is not based on a direct measurement of the TX current nor on a direct measurement of the TX-current slope. The receive signal is used as the error sensor, while the duration of the transmitter-side injection pulse is used as the actuator.

Keywords: square-wave pulse induction, bipolar PI detector, RX residual compensation, TX injection pulse, fixed compensation voltage, pulse-duration control, receive offset, current-slope compensation, prior art, metal detector.

1 Technical field and scope

The disclosure relates to square-wave pulse induction electromagnetic detectors, in particular bipolar square-wave PI metal detectors. In these systems, the TX coil current switches between defined current states instead of being charged and then fully discharged as in a conventional sawtooth-current PI detector.

This disclosure specifically concerns the compensation of a residual error visible on the receive side by an action applied on the transmit side. The residual may appear as a receive offset, a baseline displacement, a ground imbalance, target-response contamination of the control interval, a polarity-dependent residual imbalance, or as the receive-side visible consequence of a residual current slope in the TX coil.

This publication is not primarily directed to traditional sawtooth-current PI systems. In a conventional PI detector, the TX coil is charged during a transmit pulse and the stored magnetic energy is then intentionally dissipated after the pulse, generally in a damping or discharge resistor. The following pulse then starts a new charging event. Consequently, the problem of balancing a persistent current state addressed here is absent or substantially different in conventional sawtooth-current PI operation.

2 Definitions

Square-wave PI operation. Pulse induction operating mode in which the TX coil current switches between defined current states, for example between a negative-current state and a positive-current state, instead of being fully recharged from zero after each damped pulse.

TX current inclination. Residual slope, curvature, or undesired slow variation of the transmit current during a portion of the square-wave sequence where the current is intended to be substantially stable or symmetrically repeatable. The current inclination may be represented by a non-zero dI_{TX}/dt , by a slow drift of $I_{TX}(t)$, or by the receive-side visible consequence of such behavior.

Receive offset. Quasi-static or slowly varying component observed in the RX chain, preferably after the RX preamplifier, which consumes dynamic range before saturation and reduces the usable receive gain. In this disclosure, the term receive offset is to be understood broadly as a residual component observable on the RX side, including a baseline displacement, a polarity-dependent imbalance, a ground component, contamination of a control window, or the RX-side manifestation of an imperfection of the TX state. It is not assigned as a necessary consequence of RX preamplifier recovery.

Residual RX error $E_{RX}[k]$. Quantity extracted from direct ADC samples of the RX signal, or from an equivalent low-latency sampled representation obtained after a short analog capture stage or short analog integration stage, during half-cycle k . In one implementation, it is obtained by summing or averaging a short group of control windows. It is deliberately not obtained through long digital filtering or long-term averaging in the fast correction path.

TX injection pulse. Time-controlled electrical action applied to the transmit path by a switch, typically a MOSFET, which applies a fixed compensation voltage for a controlled duration.

Compensation duration T_{comp} . Conduction duration of the TX injection MOSFET. In the preferred implementation, this is the fast correction variable.

Compensation voltage V_{comp} . Fixed voltage applied by the TX injection MOSFET during the compensation pulse. V_{comp} is not amplitude-modulated by the compensation loop.

Main TX drive voltage V_{TX} . Low-voltage source used to drive the TX current state. It is distinct from the high flyback voltage generated by resonant energy transfer in the TX coil.

3 Physical problem in square-wave PI operation

Over real ground, a square-wave PI detector does not receive only target information. The RX output also depends on conductive ground response, magnetic susceptibility, mineralization, hot rocks, coil height, coil angle, sweep speed, coil-ground coupling, temperature, mechanical motion, TX asymmetry, ground-induced baseline displacement, and polarity-dependent residual imbalance in the analog chain.

A non-limiting receive model is:

$$V_{RX}(t) = V_{target}(t) + V_{ground}(t) + V_{feedthrough}(t) + V_{offset}(t) + V_{noise}(t). \quad (1)$$

$V_{target}(t)$ is the useful component to be preserved. $V_{ground}(t)$, target-response contamination of the control windows, and $V_{offset}(t)$ may displace the receive baseline, reduce the available dynamic range, and prevent the use of higher gain after preamplification. A residual slope in the TX current may also continue to excite the ground or leave the following half-cycle in a different electromagnetic initial condition.

The disclosed method uses a receive-side residual as an error measurement. The transmit path is then corrected by a fixed-voltage, duration-controlled injection pulse in order to reduce the residual visible on the receive side and the receive-side visible consequence of TX-current inclination.

4 Prior art: TX-current or current-slope feedback methods

An important family of known compensation methods seeks to reduce TX-current inclination by directly observing the TX current, or an electrical quantity directly representative of the TX current. These methods typically use a low-value sense resistor, a current-sense amplifier, an integrator, a synchronous demodulator, a comparator, a timing loop, or a negative-feedback loop. The loop then modifies a TX transition instant, controls the start or end of a rapid current-variation interval, or otherwise adjusts the TX waveform.

This family may be represented by:

$$\begin{aligned} & I_{TX}(t), \text{ TX sense voltage}(t), \text{ or } \frac{d\widehat{I}_{TX}}{dt} \\ & \Downarrow \\ & \text{TX-side measurement and feedback} \\ & \Downarrow \\ & \text{TX timing or current-control correction.} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

A representative example is Australian patent publication AU 2023204592 A1, assigned to Minelab Electronics Pty. Limited, entitled *An Improved Metal Detector*. This document describes a repeated sequence of electrical current transmitted through an inductive transmit winding, comprising a period of rapid current variation followed by a period of approximately constant non-zero current. It also describes negative-feedback control in which a transition is determined from the output of a feedback loop that measures at least part of the slope of an approximately constant-current period. In the illustrated implementation, a low-value resistor is connected in series with the transmit winding, and the corresponding sense voltage is amplified and then used by feedback integrators and timing logic to control transmitter switching.

These prior-art methods are centered on the TX-current waveform itself. Their immediate control objective is to make the TX current closer to a constant current or to reduce a measured slope in the TX-current path.

5 Practical limitations of directly measuring TX-current inclination

Direct measurement of TX-current inclination is physically difficult when the residual error is very small relative to the main coil current. In high-performance systems, the residual inclination to be measured may be very small relative to the main TX current and may occur over a short observation window. Such a residual can be difficult to measure robustly in a practical switching transmitter.

5.1 Small signal in a hostile electrical environment

The residual current-slope signal may be several orders of magnitude smaller than the main TX current. It must be measured in the presence of strong di/dt , strong dv/dt , flyback voltage, common-mode transients, switch charge injection, coil parasitics, switching transient artifacts, and electromagnetic coupling between the transmitter and the receiver. A measurement that is theoretically possible may still be poor as a real-time control input.

5.2 Amplification and integration introduce delay

To make a very small TX-current inclination measurable, the current-sense voltage generally requires amplification, filtering, synchronous detection, or integration. These operations introduce bandwidth limits, group delay, memory, noise, offset, and settling time. A loop depending on such a processed TX-current signal may be too slow to follow rapid variations in ground conditions, coil height, hot rocks, abrupt mineralization transitions, or target-response contamination of the control interval.

5.3 Series current measurement perturbs the coil system

A sense resistor inserted in the TX coil path is not electrically neutral. Even a low-value resistor adds losses, modifies the effective damping, dissipates energy, modifies LR time constants, and may disturb a resonant or quasi-resonant transmitter network. Its package inductance, routing inductance, capacitance, and common-mode voltage behavior may also become significant in a high-voltage transient system.

5.4 A fast TX-current loop may suppress useful information

A loop that aggressively forces the TX-current slope toward zero may not distinguish a transmitter imperfection, a ground response, a target response, coil motion, and a baseline displacement visible on the receive side. If the bandwidth of the loop or its correction authority is too high, the loop may partially compensate useful ground or target information that should have been preserved, particularly slow or large-amplitude target responses.

For these reasons, the method disclosed here does not use direct TX current or direct TX-current slope as the primary correction measurement. Instead, it observes the residual in the receive chain, at the point where the combined effect of the ground, target-response contamination, the coil, the transmitter, and baseline displacement effectively limits detector performance.

6 Disclosed compensation principle

At each half-cycle k , the system estimates a residual receive error $E_{RX}[k]$ from direct ADC capture windows or from an equivalent low-latency sampled representation after a short analog capture or integration stage. The error is used to update the conduction duration $T_{comp}[k]$ of a TX injection MOSFET for the next applicable half-cycle.

A non-limiting update law is:

$$E_{RX}[k] = \text{sum_or_average}(V_{RX,slot}[k, i], i = 1..N_{short}) - V_{ref}. \quad (3)$$

$$T_{comp}[k + 1] = \text{clamp}(T_{comp}[k] + K \cdot E_{RX}[k], T_{min}, T_{max}). \quad (4)$$

where N_{short} is a small integer number of fast control windows.

The essential signal flow is:

This is cross-compensation: the receiver is the error sensor, while the transmitter-side injection switch is the physical actuator. The correction path deliberately avoids slow analog integration, long digital filtering, and long averaging.

7 Preferred implementation: fixed V_{comp} , variable T_{comp}

In the preferred implementation, V_{comp} is a fixed voltage source. The compensation pulse always applies the same V_{comp} level to the TX injection path. Adaptive correction is achieved exclusively by modifying the MOSFET conduction time T_{comp} . The injected correction quantity is therefore controlled by pulse duration, not by voltage amplitude.

Parameter	Preferred implementation
Main TX drive voltage V_{TX}	Low-voltage TX drive.
TX coil current	Bipolar current between defined positive and negative current states.
Flyback voltage	Generated by resonant energy transfer; high resonant flyback voltage.
Compensation voltage V_{comp}	Fixed, not amplitude-modulated by the correction loop.
Correction variable	MOSFET conduction duration T_{comp} only.
RX residual measurement	Direct ADC sampling or equivalent low-latency sampling after a short analog capture/integration stage.
Correction rate	At each half-cycle.

The high flyback voltage is not the direct TX supply voltage. It results from resonant or flyback energy transfer involving the TX coil and associated capacitance. The bridge components in the various portions of the circuit are selected according to their actual electrical stress domains: low-voltage devices are used only in the low-voltage drive domain, and high-voltage devices are used where resonant or flyback voltage stresses appear.

8 Timing placement and half-cycle-by-half-cycle update

The compensation is updated and applied at each half-cycle. The RX residual is estimated from a short group of direct ADC capture windows or from an equivalent fast sampled post-capture value, then the resulting correction modifies the duration of the TX injection pulse for the next applicable half-cycle. This allows the compensation loop to react at the half-cycle rate without requiring long integration or slow filtering.

A practical timing constraint is:

$$t_{start_comp} + T_{comp} + t_{RX_settling} < t_{next_useful_RX}. \quad (5)$$

The compensation pulse is placed so that receive-side visible transient artifacts caused by the injection pulse do not contaminate the following useful measurement.

The method may be implemented with a single compensation variable updated half-cycle by half-cycle, or with separate compensation states according to polarity when positive and negative asymmetries must be compensated. In both cases, the central teaching remains that the correction variable is derived from an RX residual and applied on the TX side as a fixed-voltage injection duration.

9 Difference from conventional sawtooth-current PI detectors

Traditional sawtooth-current PI detectors generally do not require this compensation mechanism in the same form. In a conventional PI detector, the energy stored in the TX coil is intentionally dissipated after each transmit pulse, typically in a damping or discharge resistor. The coil current is then rebuilt by the following transmit pulse.

In such a system, there is no persistent square-current state from one half-cycle to the next that must be balanced by a fast residual-compensation loop. The dominant compensation problem and timing constraints are therefore different from those of a square-wave PI.

The disclosed method applies to square-wave PI operation, in which a current-state imbalance, residual inclination, or receive-side visible baseline error may persist across successive half-cycles if it is not actively corrected.

10 Handling slow target responses and baseline offset

In this disclosure, a slow or long-duration target response is not necessarily a problem for the compensation principle when, over the control interval used by the fast loop, it appears mainly as a slowly varying additive component. If the receive-side visible residual behaves mainly as a baseline offset, it shifts the entire received signal upward or downward without significantly modifying the relative slopes or temporal shape of the useful response. In that case, reducing the offset increases the available dynamic range without substantially modifying the useful decay information.

The compensation described here is therefore not intended to cancel the useful target response. It is intended to reduce a receive-side observable residual or baseline displacement associated with ground imbalance, coil-ground coupling, polarity-dependent residual imbalance, or receive-side visible current inclination. When the dominant error is an additive baseline term, the useful temporal slopes remain essentially preserved:

$$V_{RX}(t) = V_{useful}(t) + V_{offset} \quad (6)$$

and therefore:

$$\frac{dV_{RX}}{dt} = \frac{dV_{useful}}{dt} \quad (7)$$

for an offset that is sufficiently constant over the considered measurement interval.

Conversely, if a slow target response exhibits significant temporal variation in the control windows, it may bias the estimation of $E_{RX}[k]$. Freeze protections, slew-rate limiting, and stability classification are therefore preferable in a robust implementation.

The method may therefore include one or more optional protections:

- hard limits: $T_{min} \leq T_{comp} \leq T_{max}$;
- slew-rate limits: $|T_{comp}[k + 1] - T_{comp}[k]| \leq \Delta T_{max}$;
- temporary freeze on ADC saturation, abnormal transient condition, or blanking fault ;
- update only in windows classified as stable and non-saturated ;
- hysteresis between compensation-active, compensation-limited, and reacquisition states.

These protections do not modify the central teaching: an RX residual extracted from a short control window drives a TX-side injection duration, primarily to reduce baseline displacement and receive-side visible current-inclination effects while preserving useful temporal information.

11 Implementation variants and limits

The following implementation details are disclosed without extending the method beyond square-wave PI operation:

- RX residual measured by direct ADC sampling of the RX signal, preferably after the RX preamplifier, or by an equivalent low-latency sampled value after a short analog capture/integration stage ;
- residual estimated from a short group of fast samples or control windows ;
- absence of long analog integration, long digital filtering, or long-term averaging in the fast correction path ;
- correction updated and applied at each half-cycle ;
- fixed V_{comp} , the correction being achieved only by modifying T_{comp} ;
- actuator implemented as a MOSFET or equivalent power switch suitable for the TX injection path ;
- implementation in an FPGA, CPLD, microcontroller timer, hardware PWM, state machine, discrete logic, or mixed analog-digital circuit ;
- bounded update law, lookup table, proportional law, state-machine correction, freeze logic, or slew-rate-limited adaptation ;
- square-wave PI transmitters in which the TX coil current switches between defined current levels, in particular bipolar square-wave PI implementations.

The method is not intended to describe traditional sawtooth-current PI detectors in which the energy of the TX coil is dissipated after each pulse and the current is rebuilt by the following pulse.

12 Distinction from neighboring approaches

12.1 Distinction from direct TX-current regulation

A direct TX-current regulation method observes I_{TX} , a sense-resistor voltage, or an estimate of dI_{TX}/dt in the transmitter path. The disclosed method observes a receive residual by direct ADC sampling or by an equivalent low-latency sampled value after a short analog capture/integration stage, and uses it to control a TX injection duration. It requires neither a TX-current sense resistor, nor direct TX-current measurement, nor direct TX-current slope measurement.

12.2 Distinction from receive-side analog subtraction

A receive-side subtraction method electrically cancels a residual in the receive chain. The disclosed method instead modifies the electromagnetic state on the transmitter side by applying a duration-controlled TX injection pulse. The receiver provides the error measurement, but is not the main cancellation mechanism.

12.3 Distinction from slow ground balance

A slow ground balance based on long averaging may be stable but cannot react quickly to abrupt ground changes. The disclosed method updates at the half-cycle rate using a small number of fast samples or control windows.

12.4 Distinction from amplitude modulation

The preferred implementation does not use a continuously variable compensation voltage. Two compensation pulses have the same V_{comp} level but different durations. The duration difference is the corrective action.

12.5 Distinction from conventional sawtooth PI operation

In a conventional sawtooth-current PI detector, the energy of the TX coil is intentionally dissipated after each pulse. The following pulse starts a new current rise. The disclosed method concerns square-wave PI operation, in which the current switches between defined states and where a residual imbalance may persist from one half-cycle to the next.

13 Comparative table

Criterion	Prior art using TX-current inclination feedback	Square-wave PI method disclosed here
Detector family	Square-wave or controlled-current systems using TX-current feedback	Square-wave PI, in particular bipolar square-wave PI
Observed quantity	TX current, TX sense voltage, or TX-current slope	RX residual measured by direct ADC or equivalent low-latency post-capture value
Measurement point	Transmitter coil path	Receive chain, preferably after RX preamplifier
Typical measurement hardware	Low-value shunt, amplifier, integrator, feedback loop	Fast capture windows and timer-controlled TX injection MOSFET
Residual calculation	TX-current slope or loop error	Sum or average of a short group of control windows
Integration/filtering	Often required to observe weak TX inclination	Long integration and long filtering avoided in the fast correction path
Immediate objective	Reduce the measured TX-current inclination	Reduce receive offset and RX-visible imbalance while preserving the useful response
Control action	TX transition timing, current-loop correction, or TX waveform control	Conduction duration of a TX injection MOSFET
Compensation voltage	May depend on the loop	Fixed V_{comp}
Direct TX-current measurement	Required or implicit	Not required
Direct TX-slope measurement	Required or implicit	Not required
Series resistor in TX coil	Often present	Not required
Correction rate	Limited by the TX measurement chain and loop dynamics	Each half-cycle
Main limitation	Measurement of very small inclination, loop delay, perturbation of the coil circuit	Must avoid compensating useful slow target responses or legitimate ground responses

14 Non-limiting functional example

1. During a square-wave TX half-cycle, the detector excites the coil and acquires the useful RX measurement windows.
2. A short group of direct ADC capture windows, or an equivalent group of low-latency post-capture samples, is used to estimate the RX residual.
3. The residual is compared with a reference baseline in order to obtain $E_{RX}[k]$.
4. A bounded update law calculates the next MOSFET conduction duration $T_{comp}[k+1]$.
5. The TX injection MOSFET is activated for $T_{comp}[k + 1]$ and applies the fixed compensation voltage V_{comp} .
6. Receive blanking and settling are completed before the following useful receive measurement.
7. If a strong target, saturation, abnormal transient condition, or unstable condition is detected, the duration update is limited, slowed, or frozen.

Indicative pseudo-code:

```
for each half_cycle k:
    acquire_useful_RX_slots()

    slots = acquire_short_ADC_control_slots(count)
    E = sum_or_average(slots) - reference

    if target_detected or RX_saturated or transient_fault:
        T_comp = hold_or_slow_update(T_comp)
    else:
        T_candidate = T_comp + K * E
        T_comp = clamp_and_slew_limit(T_candidate, Tmin, Tmax, DeltaTmax)

    apply_TX_injection_pulse(voltage = fixed_V_comp,
                             duration = T_comp)
    wait_until_RX_settling_complete()
```

15 Experimental validation criteria

Reproducible validation may compare operation with and without the duration-controlled TX injection pulse. Useful observables include:

- the receive offset after the preamplifier ;
- the residual estimated from the short group of ADC or post-capture control windows ;
- the available RX gain before ADC saturation or amplifier saturation ;
- baseline stability over mineralized ground ;
- response to controlled coil-height variations ;
- response to hot rocks or local mineralization discontinuities ;
- preservation of slow or deep target responses ;
- settling time after the injection pulse ;
- stability with temperature and mechanical motion ;
- values of T_{comp} , E_{RX} , freeze indicators, saturation indicators, and quality metrics ;
- the range of TX coil current, for example defined positive and negative current states in one implementation ;
- the flyback voltage, for example a high resonant flyback voltage in one implementation.

A practical acceptance test should not only minimize the control-window residual. It should also verify that target responses are not excessively attenuated and that the compensation pulse does not introduce receive-side visible transient artifacts into the useful measurement windows.

16 Non-limiting claim-style technical formulation

The following formulations do not constitute filed patent claims. They summarize the technical teaching made public by this document.

1. Compensation method for a square-wave pulse induction electromagnetic detector comprising a transmit path and a receive chain, wherein an error representative of a receive offset, a ground imbalance, target-response contamination, or a receive-side visible current inclination is determined from a receive signal by direct ADC sampling or by an equivalent low-latency sampled representation after a short analog capture or integration stage, and wherein a compensation pulse is applied to the transmit path with a conduction duration adjusted according to said error.
2. Method according to point 1, wherein the receive-derived error is extracted from a short group of ADC capture windows or equivalent fast control samples.
3. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the fast correction path does not require long analog integration, long digital filtering, or long-term averaging.
4. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the compensation pulse is applied by an injection MOSFET temporarily applying a fixed compensation voltage V_{comp} to the transmit path.
5. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein V_{comp} is fixed and is not amplitude-modulated by the compensation loop.
6. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the adaptive correction variable is the conduction duration T_{comp} of the injection MOSFET.
7. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the correction is updated and applied at each half-cycle of the square-wave transmit sequence.
8. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the detector uses a low main TX drive voltage, while a substantially higher flyback voltage is generated by resonant energy transfer in the TX coil.
9. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the TX coil current is bipolar and switches between negative and positive current states.
10. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the duration update is limited, slew-rate limited, frozen, or weighted when a target response, receive saturation, abnormal transient condition, or slow response is detected.

11. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the compensation reduces receive offset and increases usable receive dynamic range before saturation.
12. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the compensation reduces the receive-side visible effect of a residual transmit-current inclination without requiring direct measurement of the transmit current or direct measurement of the transmit-current slope.
13. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the compensation does not require a series current-sense resistor in the transmitter coil path, the correction variable being derived from a residual observed in the receive chain.
14. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the correction avoids a fast feedback loop closed directly on the transmit current, thereby reducing the risk of suppressing a useful target response or disturbing the natural transient response of the coil circuit.
15. Method according to any one of the preceding points, wherein the method is distinct from conventional sawtooth-current PI operation, where the energy of the TX coil is intentionally dissipated after each pulse and rebuilt by the following pulse.
16. Square-wave pulse induction metal detector comprising hardware or logic configured to implement any one of the preceding methods.

17 Conclusion

The disclosed method is a compensation technique for square-wave PI operation in which the receiver is the error sensor and the transmitter injection path is the physical correction actuator. The central mechanism is neither direct TX-current regulation, nor receive-side analog subtraction, nor slow ground-balance averaging. It is a cross-compensation approach in which a receive residual, measured by direct ADC sampling or by an equivalent low-latency sampled representation after a short analog capture or integration stage over a short group of windows, drives the duration of a transmitter-side injection pulse at fixed voltage.

Even when the corrected effect may be physically interpreted as a residual TX-current inclination, the disclosed loop does not measure this inclination in the TX path. It measures its usefully observable consequence in the RX chain and acts on the TX path through an injection duration.

The preferred implementation uses a fixed V_{comp} , an injection MOSFET, and an update at each half-cycle. In one implementation, the main TX drive voltage is low, the coil current switches between defined positive and negative current states, and a substantially higher resonant flyback voltage may be generated in the TX coil circuit.

The method is distinct from prior art based on TX-current feedback, which attempts to measure a very small TX-current inclination through a current-sense element and a feedback loop. It is also distinct from conventional sawtooth-current PI operation, in which the energy of the TX coil is dissipated after each pulse and then rebuilt by the following pulse.

Practical implementations should include target-preservation logic, saturation handling, settling-time constraints, and bounded update laws so that the compensation improves baseline stability without suppressing useful target information or legitimate ground-response information.

A Notes on the referenced Minelab document

Australian patent publication AU 2023204592 A1, *An Improved Metal Detector*, is a useful example of a prior-art approach based on TX-current feedback. Its title page identifies Minelab Electronics Pty. Limited as applicant and Bruce Halcro Candy as inventor. Its abstract and claim set describe a repeated transmitted electrical current through an inductive transmit winding, periods of rapid current variation, periods of approximately constant current, and negative-feedback control using a measurement related to current slope. The description and figures also illustrate a low-value sense resistor in series with the transmit winding, amplification of the sense voltage, feedback integrators, synchronous demodulation, and timing logic controlling the transmitter switches.

The present disclosure is intentionally different. It does not require direct observation of the TX-current slope. It observes the residual in the receive chain by direct ADC sampling or by an equivalent low-latency sampled representation after a short analog capture or integration stage, and applies correction on the transmitter side through fixed-voltage pulse-duration control.

Author contributions

T. Kopp, W. Bayot, and A. Tartar contributed to the formalization of the half-cycle-by-half-cycle compensation architecture, to the distinction from direct TX-current feedback approaches, and to the drafting of this technical disclosure.

Document information

Version 1.1 — Technical disclosure

Project: ENIGMA / PI² — April 30, 2026

Subject: RX-driven compensation applied on the TX side for square-wave PI

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20154256

— End of document —